

Teaching Machine Learning in Production Engineering: Developing Practical Applications for Professional Training

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Abstract

Technological advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI), combined with the development of Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning models, have revolutionized the job market in engineering and various other professional areas. Given this scenario, it is essential that universities are prepared to include subjects that allow students to understand how these technologies work, since many professions could be transformed or even replaced using these tools. For future professionals to be able to face this new reality, it is essential that they acquire the ability to develop their own AI applications and models. The aim of this paper is to present how Machine Learning is being taught in an Information Systems subject on the Production Engineering course. The methodology adopted emphasizes practical learning, in which students develop their own applications using Machine Learning and AI techniques. As a result, innovative projects have been created, such as sentiment analysis algorithms based on movie rating databases and predictive models for choosing the Oscar winner, among others. In addition to the projects developed, one of the main gains of the course was the students' ability to analyze the results obtained from the data, making their presentations even richer and more interesting. At the end of the course, the students demonstrated an understanding of Machine Learning, but also how these technologies can contribute to their careers and academic lives.

Keywords: Machine Learning; Engineering education, Skills.

1 Introduction

Innovations related to the use of Machine Learning techniques have revolutionized both the job market and the academic environment. Traditional statistical methods, which have been widely developed and applied over decades, have shown inferior results when compared to certain approaches based on machine learning (Garcia Castro et al., 2024). Algorithms such as Random Forest, Decision Tree, Support Vector Machine (SVM), among other classification and regression models, have stood out for their ability to analyze, predict and support decision-making in various contexts (Wang et al., 2025).

Given this scenario, there is a clear need for students to be prepared to deal with these new tools and to understand how to apply them in a practical way in the field of Production Engineering. This need is intensified by the growing demand from organizations for technological innovations that guarantee greater competitiveness, cost reduction and increased market share. Companies that fail to adapt to these technologies tend to lose relevance and efficiency in their processes.

Nowadays, a huge amount of data is generated continuously in the most diverse productive and organizational sectors. However, the ability to identify where these databases are available, structure them appropriately for analysis and integrate them into practical applications still represents a significant challenge for many

professionals in the field of Production Engineering. Understanding which data can be extracted from real sources, such as public platforms or internal company systems, as well as the ability to select relevant data to improve the efficiency of production processes, is a strategic competence. At the same time, mastery of Machine Learning tools, libraries and techniques that enable the creation of predictive models and decision support systems is essential. The right choice of these tools, combined with the intelligent use of databases, can lead to significant gains in productivity, quality and competitiveness in the business environment (Al-Fakih et al., 2024; Garcia Castro et al., 2024; Gürdür Broo et al., 2022; Leung et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2025).

Although there are relatively old studies addressing the use of Machine Learning in engineering education, there is still a significant gap in the adoption of more effective methodologies that truly encourage students to integrate these tools into their technical training and future professional practice. Many of the existing works are limited to presenting generic concepts or applications, lacking a pedagogical approach that actively engages students or motivates them to develop data-driven solutions. Therefore, there is an urgent need to design more engaging educational practices that connect theory and practice, and that promote the strategic use of machine learning algorithms to address real-world engineering problems

This work aims to introduce students, in a practical and didactic way, to the main fundamentals of Machine Learning, from searching for relevant databases to extracting information and generating applicable insights. The proposal includes identifying problems, organizing data, generating context, and applying machine learning algorithms to obtain interpretable and relevant results. The approach is grounded in Problem-Based Learning (PBL) and active learning methodologies, encouraging students not only to listen and understand theoretical concepts but to apply them in real-world contexts. Based on Bloom's Taxonomy, this strategy promotes higher-order thinking by enabling students to analyze, evaluate, and create, thus developing their cognitive abilities and enhancing their capacity to use these tools in both academic and professional settings. In the next section, the methodologies used will be described, followed by a presentation of the projects developed by the students based on the activities carried out in the classroom (Dolog et al., 2016).

2 Methodology

The methodology adopted in this study was divided into two main stages. The first stage involved conducting a bibliometric and bibliographic review aimed at identifying how Machine Learning has been taught in engineering programs, particularly in the fields of Industrial Engineering, Manufacturing Engineering, and Production Engineering. For this purpose, a search strategy was developed using specific keywords related to "Machine Learning" and its applications in engineering education ("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence") AND ("teaching" OR "education" OR "curriculum development" OR "pedagogical strategies") AND ("engineering" OR "industrial engineering" OR "production engineering"). The initial search returned 16,653 articles. A filtering process was applied to select current scientific publications. Initially, a search was carried out without restrictions on the publication year. Then, to ensure the analysis was focused on recent developments, the results were refined to include only articles published in the last five years, from 2021 to 2025. This refinement resulted in a total of 9,991 articles, which were then considered for further examination in this study. This set was then refined to include only publications from the last five years and those classified under the subject areas of Industrial and Manufacturing Engineering, resulting in 248 articles.

The final dataset, composed of 248 articles, was analysed using the Web of Science's integrated bibliometric analysis tools and subsequently imported into the Bibliometrix package for deeper exploration. This dual approach allowed for the examination of several key aspects of the selected literature, including the identification of the most prolific and influential authors, as well as the institutions with the highest number of

publications in recent years. The bibliometric analysis also enabled the observation of collaboration networks—both international and institutional—and the mapping of emerging research trends within the field. Based on these findings, a selection of highly relevant articles was reviewed in full and cited throughout the literature review section, ensuring a solid foundation for understanding the state of the art in this domain

From this refined dataset, the most relevant articles were selected for in-depth analysis of the state of the art, with a particular focus on the teaching methodologies employed, the tools and technologies used, and the strategies for integrating Machine Learning content into Production Engineering curricula. Based on the insights gathered, it was possible to identify best practices, gaps, and opportunities to design a more effective instructional approach. This analysis supported the second stage of the methodology, described in the following section, which presents the development of the lesson plan implemented in the Information Systems course within the Production Engineering program.

2.1 Problem-Based Teaching Strategy for Machine Learning Applied to Production Engineering

Teaching Machine Learning algorithms in the context of Production Engineering is becoming increasingly relevant as companies strive to turn large volumes of data into strategic decisions. This work presents a teaching methodology focused on the practical application of algorithms to real-world datasets, aiming to develop students' ability to extract valuable insights and propose evidence-based solutions. Grounded in research on Problem-Based Learning (PBL) and Active Learning, the approach fosters greater student autonomy in the learning process, encouraging critical and applied knowledge construction. By understanding how the outcomes of these models can support decision support systems, students are prepared to contribute with more robust analyses and more assertive decisions in business environments.

In the initial development of the lessons, students were introduced to the fundamental concepts of Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning and Deep Learning, contextualizing their applications in the Production Engineering environment. Next, the main categories of Machine Learning problems were introduced, with an emphasis on classification and regression, exemplifying their practical applications in different organizational scenarios.

As part of the active methodology adopted, the students solved two problems based on studies previously consolidated in the literature. The first, a regression problem, consisted of estimating real estate prices from a database with descriptive attributes. The second, a classification problem, involved risk analysis for granting bank credit, using historical customer characteristics. Subsequently, public databases available on the internet were presented, and the students were encouraged to search for real data sets from their companies or workplaces, with the aim of generating insights relevant to their professional contexts.

After selecting the databases, the students were introduced to some of the main supervised Machine Learning techniques, including Decision Tree, Artificial Neural Networks, Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Random Forest. The aim was to give the students a first contact with different algorithms and their practical applications, allowing them to understand the basics of how each approach works, its advantages and limitations.

With this initial knowledge, the groups of students began to investigate what types of insights could be extracted from the selected databases, considering the business objectives or specific interests of their areas of activity. Each group was asked to think about which problem could be solved with the available database and to select the most appropriate algorithm for obtaining meaningful results. Throughout this process, the teacher provided individual guidance, monitoring the progress of each group, helping them to formulate the problem, choose the most appropriate technique and analyse the first results.

3 State of the Art on AI and Machine Learning Education in Engineering

This section provides an overview of the current landscape regarding the teaching of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) in engineering education, with a particular emphasis on Production Engineering. It introduces a bibliometric review of the main concepts and academic trends related to the integration of AI and ML in engineering curricula, highlighting how these technologies have been addressed in the educational context. Furthermore, it presents key articles that reflect the state of the art in this field, especially those that demonstrate applications in Production Engineering, such as process optimization, decision-making systems, and data-driven project development. The focus is on active learning methodologies and project-based approaches that allow students to engage in practical experiences, enhancing their ability to apply AI and ML tools in real-world, production-oriented scenarios. The next two subsections present the bibliometric analysis and a curated selection of relevant works that illustrate the pedagogical evolution and practical implementation of AI and ML education in the context of Production Engineering.

3.1 Bibliometric Review

This section presents the main results of the bibliometric review, which support the selection of articles analysed in the literature review, aiming to identify the state of the art in the field of study. The analysis enabled the identification of the most influential authors, the institutions with the highest scientific output, and the main international collaboration networks. Additionally, current research trends and recurring themes related to the teaching of Machine Learning in Engineering were mapped. These findings provided objective criteria for selecting the most relevant and up-to-date works that form the theoretical foundation of this study.

Figure 1. Annual distribution of publications retrieved from the Web of Science database during the analyze period

Figure 1 displays the distribution of publications over the five selected years. It can be observed that, so far, 2025 has a lower number of publications, which is likely because the year is still in its early stages. The year 2024 stands out with the highest number of publications, reaching a total of 83 articles. This data highlights a significant increase in scientific interest in the topic, reflecting its growing relevance within the academic community.

About the scientific output of the authors in the dataset analysed, Kim Phuc Tran, a researcher at the École Nationale Supérieure des Arts et Industries Textiles, stands out as the author with the highest number of publications in the period, totalling four articles. His contributions focus on topics directly related to Production Engineering, with an emphasis on Statistical Process Control (SPC), compositional data analysis, industrial process optimization and the application of statistical and machine learning tools.

Tran's articles include: "Monitoring autocorrelated compositional data vectors using an enhanced residuals Hotelling T^2 control chart", "Analyzing abnormal pattern of Hotelling T^2 control chart for compositional data using artificial neural networks", "Incorporating principal component analysis into Hotelling T^2 control chart for compositional data monitoring" and "Optimal design and evaluation of adaptive EWMA monitoring schemes for Inverse Maxwell distribution" (Imran et al., 2023; Saghir et al., 2023; Zaidi et al., 2023a, 2023b).

Figure 2. Number of Publications per Author in the Selected Dataset from Web of Science During the Analyzed Period

These contributions reflect a consistent effort to integrate Machine Learning tools into the context of production engineering and its teaching, promoting improvements in the efficiency and accuracy of industrial process monitoring, as well as offering practical applications relevant to the training of engineers in the era of Industry 4.0.

3.2 State of art in the machine learning and IA for engineering

Modran et al. (2021) point out that, according to the World Economic Forum (2020), around 75 million jobs are expected to disappear due to the advance of artificial intelligence. On the other hand, it is estimated that approximately 183 million new jobs will be created, which shows that AI represents not only a challenge, but also a significant job creation opportunity. From this perspective, the authors stress the importance of preparing students for this new reality, emphasizing that it is essential to train them to acquire the skills needed to use artificial intelligence, especially in a context of accelerated digital transformation.

Romero et al. (2021) present an innovative proposal for teaching mathematics in higher education through the EXPLORIA project, which integrates STEAM subjects into a sequential learning process based on active methodologies. The article highlights the need to rethink traditional teaching practices, especially in engineering courses, emphasizing the importance of connecting mathematics to real-life situations, interdisciplinary challenges and applied projects. By integrating mathematical content with subjects such as physics, design and art, the authors observed a significant increase in students' motivation, involvement and positive perception of mathematics. In addition, concrete improvements in academic performance were recorded, most notably a reduction in failure rates and an increase in final averages. The study shows that learning experiences that are more connected to real technologies, such as computational techniques, artificial intelligence and machine learning, contribute to the development of essential skills for training engineers who are prepared for the challenges of the future. Thus, the article reinforces the relevance of integrated, student-

centered methodologies as an effective way of transforming mathematics teaching into a significant element of professional training.

The study proposes the development and implementation of a system made up of hardware and software based on artificial intelligence, aimed at training engineers. The aim is to enable students to understand the fundamentals of machine learning through interaction with modern educational technologies. The main results of the research indicate that the students and engineers involved in the experiment acquired relevant knowledge about machine learning, demonstrating the potential of AI as an effective pedagogical tool in training professionals prepared for the challenges of the future (Modran et al., 2021).

The three articles featuring author Kim Phuc Tran, the most recurrent among the 248 articles analyzed in the bibliometric review, make significant contributions to the field of production engineering, especially in the context of quality and statistical process monitoring. The papers address specific problems related to statistical control charts, with a focus on autocorrelated compositional data, a common type of data in industrial applications (Imran et al., 2023; Zaidi et al., 2023b, 2023a).

In one of these studies, artificial neural networks were used to detect anomalous behavior, i.e. deviations from the normal pattern of the data, even under conditions of autocorrelation. This approach represents an important innovation, combining artificial intelligence and deep learning tools with classical statistical methods, such as Hotelling T^2 control charts and principal component analysis (PCA) (Zaidi et al., 2023b).

The contribution of these articles goes beyond academic research, as they show the potential of neural networks in improving consolidated production engineering tools, such as quality control charts. Such practical application can be especially useful in engineering education, helping to motivate students to learn more about machine learning, artificial intelligence and deep learning, by understanding how these technologies can improve traditional tools that are already part of their technical (Imran et al., 2023; Zaidi et al., 2023b, 2023a)

4 Developed Projects: AI Applications in Engineering Education

The systematic literature review supported the design of the pedagogical approach adopted in this study, highlighting that there is already a significant interest in teaching topics related to Industry 4.0 in engineering education. Although the reviewed methodologies vary in structure and implementation, they share key characteristics: the use of real-world data, the promotion of student autonomy, and the application of machine learning tools to solve relevant problems. These common elements served as a foundation for the development of the classroom activities and guided the instructional choices described in the following sections.

During the course, several projects were developed by different groups of students, each exploring practical applications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) aimed at educational engineering and data analysis. This topic will present some of the most relevant projects, selected based on originality, technical complexity and possibilities for future application.

4.1 Project 1 – Sentimental Analysis in Social Media

The first project focused on sentiment analysis in social media posts, aiming to evaluate the effectiveness of different machine learning algorithms using multimodal inputs (text and image). The students conducted a literature review on multimodal sentiment analysis and explored several datasets from platforms such as Instagram (via InstaLoader), Amazon Reviews, commodity market news, and public repositories like Kaggle and Hugging Face. They faced real-world data collection and preprocessing challenges, especially regarding balancing datasets and cleaning social media comments with informal or ironic language.

To address the problem, the students tested a range of classification algorithms, including Decision Tree, Neural Network, Naive Bayes, and Linear Regression. The most successful results were achieved using a Decision Tree model trained on over 500,000 Amazon reviews and validated on social media comments, particularly from Starbucks campaigns. The students also implemented a DistilBERT-based model from Hugging Face for comparison, which allowed them to understand the practical trade-offs between traditional and deep learning approaches.

Evaluation metrics included accuracy, F1-score, precision, recall, ROC AUC, average precision, and cross-validation. Among all the approaches, the Decision Tree model stood out with a solid overall performance, reaching a mean cross-validation score of 0.872, as well as high interpretability and ease of application. The project offered students hands-on experience with real datasets, algorithm evaluation, model tuning, and performance interpretation — reinforcing core concepts in machine learning and their applicability to engineering problems involving human behaviour data.

4.2 Project 2 – Predicting Oscar Winners Using Machine Learning

In the second project, the students developed a system to predict the winner of the Best Picture category at the Oscars, using data science and machine learning. The database was created with information on the last 24 winners, collected from the Rotten Tomatoes website, a respected source in the film industry. The data was organized in Google Sheets and then transferred to Excel, where it went through a process of cleaning and selecting variables, transforming qualitative data into quantitative data, except for the “winner” variable.

With the base prepared, the students applied different machine learning techniques in Python. The algorithm that performed best was Random Forest, which was used to train and test the model based on information from the films. Among the contenders for the 2024 Oscars were *Furiosa*, *Dune*, *Planet of the Apes*, *Madame Teia*, *Rivals*, *Imaginary Friends*, *Civil War*, *Fall*, *The Idea of You* and *Monkey Man* - the latter was predicted by the model as the likely winner.

Although the prediction didn't come true, the project provided the students with significant learning in data collection, organization and processing, as well as the application and evaluation of predictive models.

4.3 Project 3 – Construction Decision System

The third project aimed to develop a decision support system based on the collection, processing and analysis of real data from a construction company. Using JavaScript and process automation, the system was applied to the context of project management in the construction industry, with a focus on controlling deadlines and managing the sending and receiving of internal and external documents.

Based on requirements control spreadsheet, code was created to automatically identify which documents were causing the greatest delays, both in internal processes and in dealings with public bodies. The system displayed alerts with the longest analysis times, helping to prioritize the most critical projects and documents.

Analysis of the data revealed that 75.55% of the works had time amendments, with delays in 48.94% of the cases in relation to the planned time - figures compatible with the literature on delays in public works. Thus, the system helped transform operational data into useful knowledge for decision-making and organizational control. Furthermore, improvements were suggested, such as the use of trend analysis techniques and the implementation of automatic notifications to reinforce the system's efficiency.

4.4 Lessons Learned and Project Comparison

Throughout the development of the projects, students learned how to identify and access relevant databases using three different strategies. Based on the chosen datasets and the insights they intended to generate, they

were also able to select appropriate tools, programming languages, and types of machine learning applications to pursue. This autonomy in decision-making was one of the key learning outcomes of the activity. All three projects achieved satisfactory results and sparked students' interest in further exploring Machine Learning, Deep Learning, and Artificial Intelligence—indicating that the main educational objective of the course was successfully met.

5 Conclusion

Current literature highlights the growing need to improve the teaching of emerging technologies such as Machine Learning, Deep Learning, and Artificial Intelligence in engineering education. Several studies already point to this gap and emphasize the urgency of equipping students with skills in these areas, which are rapidly evolving and increasingly demanded in the professional landscape.

The outcomes of this work demonstrate that the classroom methodology was effective. The three student projects clearly showed an understanding of database handling, information processing, and the application of algorithms in decision support systems. As a future direction, it is recommended to maintain and expand elective courses focused on these technologies, reinforcing both the practical and theoretical training of students.

References

- Al-Fakih, A., Abdurraheem, A., & Kaka, S. (2024). Application of machine learning and deep learning in geothermal resource development: Trends and perspectives. *Deep Underground Science and Engineering*, 3(3), 286–301. <https://doi.org/10.1002/dug2.12098>
- Dolog, P., Thomsen, L. L., & Thomsen, B. (2016). Assessing problem-based learning in a software engineering curriculum using Bloom's taxonomy and the IEEE software engineering body of knowledge. *ACM Transactions on Computing Education*, 16(3), 1–41. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2845091>
- Garcia Castro, R. A., Chura-Quispe, G., Velarde Molina, J. F., Espinoza Ramos, L. A., & Almonte Durand, C. A. (2024). Bibliometric review on teaching methods with artificial intelligence in education. *Online Journal of Communication and Media Technologies*, 14(2), e202419. <https://doi.org/10.30935/ojcm/14367>
- Gürdür Broo, D., Kaynak, O., & Sait, S. M. (2022). Rethinking engineering education at the age of Industry 5.0. *Journal of Industrial Information Integration*, 25, 100311. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jii.2021.100311>
- Imran, M., Dai, H.-L., Zaidi, F. S., Tran, K. P., Abbas, Z., & Nazir, H. Z. (2023). Incorporating principal component analysis into Hotelling T² control chart for compositional data monitoring. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 186, 109755. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2023.109755>
- Leung, M., Lu, X., Chen, D., & Lu, M. (2008). Impacts of teaching approaches on learning approaches of construction engineering students: A comparative study between Hong Kong and Mainland China. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 97(2), 135–145. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2008.tb00963.x>
- Modran, H. A., Ursutiu, D., Samoila, C., & Chamunorwa, T. (2021). Learning methods based on artificial intelligence in educating engineers for the new jobs of the 5th industrial revolution. In *Proceedings of the 2021 International Conference on Innovative Technologies and Learning* (pp. 561–571). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-68201-9_55
- Saghir, A., Hu, X., Tran, K. P., & Song, Z. (2023). Optimal design and evaluation of adaptive EWMA monitoring schemes for inverse Maxwell distribution. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 181, 109290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2023.109290>
- Wang, C., Li, T., Lu, Z., Wang, Z., Alballa, T., Alhabeeb, S. A., Albely, M. S., & Khalifa, H. A. E.-W. (2025). Application of artificial intelligence for feature engineering in education sector and learning science. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, 110, 108–115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aej.2024.09.100>
- World Economic Forum. (2020, May 20). Reskilling revolution platform. <https://www.weforum.org/projects/reskilling-revolution-platform>
- Zaidi, F. S., Dai, H.-L., Imran, M., & Tran, K. P. (2023a). Analyzing abnormal pattern of Hotelling T² control chart for compositional data using artificial neural networks. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 180, 109254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2023.109254>
- Zaidi, F. S., Dai, H.-L., Imran, M., & Tran, K. P. (2023b). Monitoring autocorrelated compositional data vectors using an enhanced residuals Hotelling T² control chart. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 181, 109280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2023.109280>